

ImproRisk

“Exposure Assessment of Acetamiprid”

ImproRisk Scientific Report

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1 Summary

Acetamiprid is an organic compound with the chemical formula $C_{10}H_{11}ClN_4$. It is an odorless neonicotinoid insecticide produced under the trade names Assail, and Chipco by Aventis CropSciences. It is systemic and intended to control sucking insects (Thysanoptera, Hemiptera, mainly aphids) on crops such as leafy vegetables, citrus fruits, pome fruits, grapes, cotton, cole crops, and ornamental plants. It is also a key pesticide in commercial cherry farming due to its effectiveness against the larvae of the cherry fruit fly.

Acetamiprid is an insecticide belonging to the chloropyridinyl neonicotinoids, this family of insecticides was introduced in the early 1990s. This compound is an insecticide that is introduced for controlling pests, but also for domestic use to control fleas on cats and dogs.

In the current report the dietary exposure of the target population is studied using ImproRisk model v.0.3.2. The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the chronic dietary Acetamiprid intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI) of $24 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ body weight (b.w.) per week and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary Acetamiprid exposure.

Mean and 95th percentile exposure for the Middle-bound scenario were calculated as 0.038 and $0.097 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ b.w. per day. It was found that in all three scenarios (LB, MB, UB) the whole population was exposed much lower than the ADI value of $25 \mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ b.w. per day. Toddlers and infants had higher exposure than the other population classes due to their lower body weight. In all population classes the exposure was much lower than the ADI for Acetamiprid intake, 150 times lower for infants and toddlers and almost 1500 times lower for adults and elderly. There was no significant difference in Acetamiprid intake between genders and geographical areas.

The contribution to the total Acetamiprid exposure was mainly from fruits. Apples (15.6%), Potatoes (12.9%), Olive oil (6.5), Bananas (5.8%), Orange juice (5.5%), followed by grapes, oranges, cereal-based food and pears (2.4-2.8%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Acetamiprid intake. Due to an overestimation of the exposure by the application of the substitution method in the occurrence data some food categories appeared in the main contributors even they were not contaminated with Acetamiprid. The most contaminated fruits were apples, grapes, pears and oranges.

2 Introduction

Acetamiprid is an α -chloro-N-heteroaromatic compound. It is a neonicotinoid with a chloropyridinyl group and it is comparable to other neonicotinoids such as imidacloprid, nitenpyram and thiacloprid. These substances all have a 6-chloro-3-pyridine methyl group but differ in the nitroguanidine, nitromethylene, or cyanoamidine substituent on an acyclic or cyclic moiety. There are two isomeric forms in acetamiprid with E and Z-configurations of the cyanoimino group. There are also a variety of stable conformers due to the rotation of single bonds in the N-pyridylmethylamino group. The E-conformer is more stable than the Z-conformer and assumed to be the active form. In solution, two different E-conformers exist which slowly change into each other.

Acetamiprid is a nicotine-like substance and reacts to the body in a similar way as nicotine. Nicotine is a natural insecticide of which many man-made insecticides are derivatives. Acetamiprid is a nicotinic agonist that reacts with nicotinic acetylcholine receptors (nACh-R). These receptors are located in the post-synaptic dendrites of all neurons in the brain, spinal cord, ganglia and muscular junctions. The activation of the nACh-R receptors causes hyperactivity and muscle spasms, and eventually death. Acetamiprid is highly toxic to insects, but less to mammals.

Acetamiprid is used to protect a variety of crops, plants and flowers. It can be used combined with another pesticide with a different mode of action. This way the developing of resistance by pest species can be prevented. According to the US EPA acetamiprid could play a role in battling resistance in the species: Bemisia, greenhouse whiteflies and western flower thrips. Neonicotinoids act as agonists for nAChR and are selectively toxic to insects versus mammals, because of a higher potency on insect than mammalian nAChRs. This increases their suitability as pesticides.

Although mammalian toxicity is recorded as low, high doses of acetamiprid are recorded to be toxic to humans. Acetamiprid is classified as unlikely to be a human carcinogen. Acetamiprid has a low acute and chronic toxicity in mammals with no evidence of carcinogenicity, neurotoxicity or mutagenicity. It is classified as toxicity category rating II in acute oral studies with rats, toxicity category III in acute dermal and inhalation studies with rats, and toxicity category IV in primary eye and skin irritation studies with rabbits.

2.1 Background

2.2 Terms of Reference

The aim of this risk assessment study was to estimate the chronic dietary Acetamiprid intake of the population in Cyprus, to compare this exposure estimate with the Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI) of 24 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ body weight (b.w.) per week and to calculate the contribution rate of the major food groups to the dietary Acetamiprid exposure.

3 Data and Methodology

3.1 Occurrence data

3.1.1 Data collection and validation

Acetamiprid occurrence data in food were extracted from LIMS for the years 2014-2020, and are shown in Tables 3.1. Only plant origin food was selected to be used in the calculation of the exposure. For results below LOD, EFSA's assumption was applied. Occurrence results below the LOQ were set to zero for the Low-bound scenario, half the LOQ for the Middle-bound scenario and LOQ for the Upper-bound scenario. Dilution factors were applied in order to estimate concentrations for different coffee and cocoa beverages, tea beverages and liquid children and infant milk. The aggregated occurrence dataset is: Acetamiprid 2014-2020_Aggregated_Plant origin_Final.xlsx with occurrence estimates for 208 food items.

Table 3.1 shows the aggregated occurrence values used in the exposure assessment of Acetamiprid

Table 3.1: Aggregated occurrence values for Acetamiprid

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A03GG	Coffee, cocoa, tea and infusions	1	55		0.0007	0.0080	0.0153
A03GH	Ingredients for coffee, cocoa, tea, and herbal infusions	2	55		0.0007	0.0080	0.0153
A03GJ	Coffee ingredients	3	9		0.0000	0.0131	0.0261
A03HQ	Tea leaves derivatives and tea ingredients	3	42		0.0009	0.0069	0.0130
A03JB	Flowers used for herbal infusions	3	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A03JK	Herbal infusion materials from leaves and herbs	3	2		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A04KK	Teas leaves, dry and/or fermented, and similar	4	42		0.0009	0.0069	0.0130
A0C6A	Coffee ingredients (RPC derivatives)	4	1		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A0D9E	Chamomile and similar-	4	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A0D9J	Coffee beans and similar-	4	8		0.0000	0.0134	0.0269
A03GK	Coffee beans, green	5	1		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A03GQ	Instant coffee powder	5	1		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A03JC	Chamomile	5	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A011X	Legumes, nuts, oilseeds and spices	1	167		0.0003	0.0067	0.0130
A016S	Spices	2	22		0.0000	0.0092	0.0184
A01AY	Processed legumes, nuts, oilseeds and spices	2	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A04RG	Legumes	2	133		0.0004	0.0047	0.0091
A04RH	Nuts, oilseeds and oilfruits	2	11		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A011Y	Legumes fresh seeds (beans, peas etc.)	3	27		0.0000	0.0046	0.0093
A012R	Pulses (dried legume seeds)	3	106		0.0005	0.0048	0.0090
A014C	Tree nuts	3	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A015F	Oilseeds	3	10		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A017X	Seed spices	3	10		0.0000	0.0065	0.0130
A019Z	Root and rhizome spices	3	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01AK	Bud spices	3	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01AZ	Canned or jarred legumes	3	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A011Z	Beans (fresh seeds without pods) and similar-	4	4		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A012G	Peas (without pods) and similar-	4	23		0.0000	0.0046	0.0091
A012S	Beans (dry) and similar-	4	72		0.0007	0.0047	0.0087
A01BC	Canned or jarred peas	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0CGQ	Coriander seeds and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A0CGX	Ginger roots and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0CHA	Capers buds and similar-	4	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0CZA	Cumin seed and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0CZF	Anise seed and similar-	4	8		0.0000	0.0063	0.0125
A0DBP	Sunflower seeds and similar-	4	2		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A0DBQ	Sesame seeds and similar-	4	8		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A0DCD	Peas (dry) and similar-	4	15		0.0000	0.0048	0.0097
A0DCE	Lentils (dry) and similar-	4	19		0.0000	0.0049	0.0097
A0DYJ	Chestnuts and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A012A	Broad beans (without pods)	5	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A012J	Garden peas (without pods)	5	23		0.0000	0.0046	0.0091
A013H	Broad beans (dry)	5	7		0.0000	0.0043	0.0086
A013J	Garden peas (dry)	5	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A013M	Chickpeas (dry)	5	13		0.0000	0.0048	0.0096
A013N	Black eyed peas (dry)	5	18		0.0027	0.0066	0.0105
A013Q	Lentils (dry)	5	19		0.0000	0.0049	0.0097
A014J	Chestnuts	5	1		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A015K	Sesame seeds	5	8		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A015L	Sunflower seeds	5	2		0.0000	0.0250	0.0500
A017Y	Anise seed	5	8		0.0000	0.0063	0.0125
A018D	Coriander seed	5	1		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A018E	Cumin seed	5	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01AB	Ginger roots	5	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01AM	Capers buds	5	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A000J	Grains and grain-based products	1	216		0.0008	0.0053	0.0098
A000K	Cereals and cereal primary derivatives	2	202		0.0009	0.0054	0.0100
A00CV	Breakfast cereals	2	14		0.0000	0.0036	0.0071
A000L	Cereal grains (and cereal-like grains)	3	155		0.0011	0.0056	0.0101
A04KS	Cereal and cereal-like flours	3	42		0.0000	0.0048	0.0095
A04LK	Processed and mixed breakfast cereals	3	14		0.0000	0.0036	0.0071
A0BY1	Groats	3	5		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A000F	Oat and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A000S	Maize and similar-	4	4		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A000Y	Common millet and similar-	4	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A001C	Rice and similar-	4	122		0.0014	0.0058	0.0101
A001M	Wheat and similar-	4	19		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A002G	Buckwheat flour	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A002L	Barley flour	4	11		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A002Y	Oat flour	4	4		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A002Z	Oat groats	4	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A003J	Rye flour	4	5		0.0000	0.0030	0.0060
A003X	Wheat flour	4	21		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A004G	Bulgur	4	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A04KH	Buckwheat and other pseudo-cereals and similar-	4	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A04QY	Cereal flakes and similar	4	14		0.0000	0.0036	0.0071

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A0D9Y	Barley and similar-	4	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A000A	Teff grain	5	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A000N	Buckwheat	5	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A000P	Barley grains	5	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A000R	Quinoa grain	5	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A001D	Rice grain	5	122		0.0014	0.0058	0.0101
A003M	Rye flour, wholemeal	5	5		0.0000	0.0030	0.0060
A004C	Wheat flour, durum	5	5		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A00DN	Processed oat-based flakes	5	6		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A00DY	Processed rye-based flakes	5	8		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A001E	Rice grain, brown	6	11		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A00ZR	Starchy roots or tubers and products thereof, sugar plants	1	94		0.0000	0.0036	0.0073
A00ZS	Starchy roots and tubers	2	94		0.0000	0.0036	0.0073
A00ZY	Tropical root and tuber vegetables	3	7		0.0000	0.0036	0.0071
A0DPP	Potatoes and similar-	3	87		0.0000	0.0036	0.0073
A00ZT	Potatoes	4	87		0.0000	0.0036	0.0073
A04JX	Cassava roots and similar-	4	7		0.0000	0.0036	0.0071
A010B	Taros	5	7		0.0000	0.0036	0.0071
A01BS	Fruit and fruit products	1	485		0.0036	0.0073	0.0110
A04RK	Fruit used as fruit	2	480		0.0035	0.0072	0.0109
A01BT	Citrus fruits	3	112		0.0018	0.0056	0.0093
A01DG	Pome fruits	3	87		0.0064	0.0095	0.0126
A01DT	Berries and small fruits	3	120		0.0047	0.0087	0.0126

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A01GE	Stone fruits	3	63		0.0057	0.0089	0.0121
A01HE	Miscellaneous fruits with edible peel	3	15		0.0000	0.0058	0.0117
A01JS	Miscellaneous fruits with inedible peel, small	3	14		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A01LA	Miscellaneous fruits with inedible peel, large	3	69		0.0001	0.0040	0.0080
A01MA	Dried fruit	3	5		0.0130	0.0165	0.0200
A01BX	Lemons and similar-	4	25		0.0032	0.0062	0.0092
A01CB	Mandarins and similar-	4	24		0.0000	0.0035	0.0071
A01CP	Oranges and similar-	4	62		0.0021	0.0062	0.0103
A01CX	Grapefruits and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A01DH	Apples and similar-	4	41		0.0098	0.0122	0.0147
A01DN	Pears and similar-	4	42		0.0037	0.0075	0.0113
A01DV	Grapes and similar fruits	4	56		0.0101	0.0140	0.0178
A01DZ	Strawberries and similar-	4	60		0.0000	0.0040	0.0080
A01ED	Cane fruits	4	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01GG	Cherries and similar-	4	19		0.0111	0.0150	0.0189
A01GL	Peaches and similar-	4	26		0.0029	0.0057	0.0085
A01GP	Plums and similar-	4	10		0.0021	0.0059	0.0096
A01HH	Table olives and similar-	4	8		0.0000	0.0088	0.0175
A01LN	Guavas and similar-	4	2		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A01MB	Dried prunes	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01ME	Dried vine fruits (raisins etc.)	4	3		0.0217	0.0242	0.0267
A04JJ	Blueberries and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A04JS	Bananas and similar-	4	22		0.0000	0.0048	0.0095

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A0DPV	Pineapples and similar-	4	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0DQC	Granate apples and similar-	4	31		0.0001	0.0033	0.0064
A0DQE	Papayas and similar-	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0DQF	Mangoes and similar-	4	5		0.0000	0.0045	0.0090
A0DQP	Avocados and similar-	4	5		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0DRG	Kiwi fruits and similar-	4	14		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A0DRY	Figs and similar-	4	7		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A0DVX	Apricots and similar-	4	8		0.0063	0.0084	0.0106
A0DVY	Loquats and similar-	4	4		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A01BP	Table olives	5	8		0.0000	0.0088	0.0175
A01BY	Lemons	5	25		0.0032	0.0062	0.0092
A01CY	Grapefruits	5	1		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A01DJ	Apples	5	41		0.0098	0.0122	0.0147
A01DL	Loquats	5	4		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A01DP	Pears	5	40		0.0039	0.0077	0.0115
A01DQ	Nashi pears	5	2		0.0000	0.0037	0.0075
A01EA	Strawberries	5	60		0.0000	0.0040	0.0080
A01EN	Raspberries and similar-	5	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01EY	Blueberries	5	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01GF	Apricots	5	8		0.0063	0.0084	0.0106
A01GK	Cherries (sweet)	5	19		0.0111	0.0150	0.0189
A01GQ	Plums	5	10		0.0021	0.0059	0.0096
A01HG	Figs	5	7		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A01JT	Kiwi fruits (green, red, yellow)	5	14		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A01LB	Avocados	5	5		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01LF	Mangoes	5	5		0.0000	0.0045	0.0090
A01LG	Papayas	5	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01LH	Granate apples	5	31		0.0001	0.0033	0.0064
A01LP	Pineapples	5	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0CGD	Guavas	5	2		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A0DTY	Blackberries and similar-	5	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0DVE	Table grapes and similar-	5	56		0.0101	0.0140	0.0178
A0DZB	Oranges	5	62		0.0021	0.0062	0.0103
A01DX	Table grapes	6	56		0.0101	0.0140	0.0178
A01EE	Blackberries	6	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A01EP	Raspberries (red and yellow)	6	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A032F	Sugar and similar, confectionery and water-based sweet desserts	1	14		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A04PA	Sugar and other sweetening ingredients (excluding intensive sweeteners)	2	14		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A033J	Honey	3	14		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A036M	Animal and vegetable fats and oils and primary derivatives thereof	1	26		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A0F3D	Animal and vegetable fats/oils	2	26		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A036N	Vegetable fats and oils, edible	3	26		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A036P	Olive oils	4	26		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200
A036Q	Olive oil, virgin or extra-virgin	5	26		0.0000	0.0100	0.0200

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A03PV	Food products for young population	1	57		0.0000	0.0035	0.0069
A03PY	Infant and follow-on formulae	2	32		0.0000	0.0033	0.0066
A03QX	Processed cereal-based food for infants and young children	2	13		0.0000	0.0048	0.0096
A03RC	Ready-to-eat meal for infants and young children	2	12		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A03QZ	Cereals with an added high protein food which have to be reconstituted with water or other protein-free liquid	3	13		0.0000	0.0048	0.0096
A03RD	Ready-to-eat vegetable-based meal for children	3	1		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A03RJ	Ready-to-eat fruit-based meal for children	3	11		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A0EQL	Follow-on formulae	3	13		0.0000	0.0031	0.0062
A0EQM	Infant formulae	3	19		0.0000	0.0034	0.0068
A03PZ	Infant formulae, powder	4	19		0.0000	0.0034	0.0068
A03QK	Follow-on formulae, powder	4	13		0.0000	0.0031	0.0062
A039K	Fruit and vegetable juices and nectars (including concentrates)	1	20		0.0000	0.0053	0.0105
A03BM	Concentrated or dehydrated fruit/vegetables juices	2	2		0.0000	0.0088	0.0175
A0BX9	Fruit / vegetable juices and nectars	2	18		0.0000	0.0049	0.0097
A03BB	Fruit nectars (min. 25-50% fruit as defined in EU legislation)	3	3		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A0BY4	Fruit juices (100% from named source)	3	15		0.0000	0.0048	0.0097

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A0ETV	Fruit/vegetable juice concentrate	3	2		0.0000	0.0088	0.0175
A039T	Juice, cranberry	4	1		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A03AF	Juice, pineapple	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A03AM	Juice, orange	4	13		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A03BF	Nectar, mango	4	1		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A03BG	Nectar, orange	4	2		0.0000	0.0050	0.0100
A03BN	Fruit juice concentrates	4	2		0.0000	0.0088	0.0175
A03CA	Juice concentrate, orange	5	2		0.0000	0.0088	0.0175
A03LZ	Alcoholic beverages	1	17		0.0000	0.0026	0.0053
A03MS	Wine and wine-like drinks	2	17		0.0000	0.0026	0.0053
A03MT	Wine	3	17		0.0000	0.0026	0.0053
A03MV	Wine, white	4	8		0.0000	0.0028	0.0056
A03MX	Wine, red	4	9		0.0000	0.0025	0.0050
A03KE	Instant coffee (beverage)	4	21		0.0000	0.0002	0.0003
A03KK	Iced coffee	4	12		0.0000	0.0006	0.0011
A03KG	Coffee with milk or cream	4	12		0.0000	0.0006	0.0011
A03KB	Coffee espresso (beverage)	4	15		0.0000	0.0014	0.0029
A03KH	Coffee drink, cappuccino	5	21		0.0000	0.0006	0.0011
A03KA	Coffee beverages	3	35		0.0000	0.0006	0.0011
A03KD	Coffee (weak strength) beverage	4	11		0.0000	0.0006	0.0011
A03KF	Coffee beverage decaffeinated	4	11		0.0000	0.0006	0.0011
A03QF	Infant formula, milk-based, liquid	5	12		0.0000	0.0004	0.0008

FoodEx2 Code	FoodEx2 Name	Level	N	% Left censored	LB mean (mg/kg)	MB mean (mg/kg)	UB mean (mg/kg)
A03QR	Follow-on formula, milk-based, liquid	5	12		0.0000	0.0004	0.0008
A03LB	Tea beverages	3	12		0.0000	0.0001	0.0002
A03LG	Herbal and other non-tea infusions	3	12		0.0000	0.0001	0.0002
A03KY	Cocoa beverages	3	22		0.0000	0.0001	0.0003

3.2 Consumption data

Food consumption data were obtained from the EUMenu project funded by EFSA and the dietary survey was carried out in the years 2014-2018. The consumption data was the result of a survey of 1661 participants (male and female). The survey covered all five cities of Cyprus, rural and urban regions, and also all days of the week and the four seasons. The population classes and the number of participants in each class were: [a] infants: 3-11 months (269), [b] toddlers: 12-35 months (279), [c] other children: 3-9 years (300), [d] adolescents: 10-17 years (274), [e] adults: 18-64 years (275) and [f] elderly: 65-74 years (264). The consumption dataset is: Consumption data_CY population.xlsx with 82921 occasions.

Table 3.2: Food consumption survey details

Country	Start Year	End Year	Survey Code	Method of Survey	EU Menu Population	Survey Name	Survey Reference publication
CYPRUS	2014	2018		24h recall	1661	EU-Menu	

3.2.1 Target population

Figure 3.1 shows the number of subjects per population class and categorization between the two genders.

Figure 3.1: Number of subjects in the survey

3.2.2 Weight coefficients to adjust the sample for non – representativeness within the population

Table 3.3: Weight coefficients used

Gender	Population class	Weight coefficient	Number of subjects
FEMALE	Adolescents	265	137
FEMALE	Adults	2,044	139
FEMALE	Elderly	303	129
FEMALE	Infants	32	134
FEMALE	Other children	226	145
FEMALE	Toddlers	66	137
MALE	Adolescents	281	134
MALE	Adults	1,993	134
MALE	Elderly	277	130
MALE	Infants	36	134
MALE	Other children	229	151
MALE	Toddlers	70	137

3.3 Food classification

Consumption and occurrence data were both codified according to the FoodEx2 classification system developed by EFSA. At the moment of the generation of the present report the MTX catalogue version 13.1 was applied.

3.4 Methodologies

3.4.1 Chronic dietary exposure

Dietary exposure was assessed at individual level by multiplying the average daily consumption of each food with the corresponding mean occurrence estimated for Acetamiprid summing up the respective intakes throughout the diet and finally dividing the results by the individual's body weight.

3.4.2 Dietary exposure assessment model

Dietary exposure assessment was performed using ImproRisk model version 0.3.2

4 Dietary Exposure Assessment

Table 4.1 presents the substance information.

Table 4.1: Substance information

key	
Chemical Substance	Acetamiprid
Substance Category	Pesticide
Reference value	25 µg/Kg b.w. per day
Type of reference value	Acceptable Daily Intake (ADI)

Table 4.2 presents the exposure statistics.

Table 4.2: Summary exposure statistics of Acetamiprid

Scenario			
key	LB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)	MB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)	UB (µg/Kg b.w. per day)
Min	0	0	0
Max	0.311	0.613	1.226
Mean	0.008	0.038	0.068
SD	0.014	0.037	0.064
P25	0	0.018	0.034
Median	0.002	0.03	0.054
P75	0.011	0.046	0.083
P95	0.032	0.097	0.171
pctOver	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%

* pctOver:Percentage of population above the reference value

Mean and 95th percentile exposure for the Middle-bound scenario were calculated as 0.038 and 0.097 µg/kg b.w. per day (Table 4.2). It was found that in all three scenarios (LB, MB, UB) the whole population was exposed much lower than the ADI value of 25 µg/Kg b.w. per day, as also shown in Figures 4.1 and 4.2.

4.1 Distribution of exposure

Probability distribution

Figure 4.1 shows the probability distribution of the exposure.

Figure 4.1: Probability distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

Cumulative distribution

Figure 4.2 shows the cumulative distribution of exposure.

Figure 4.2: Cumulative distribution of exposure at the MB scenario

4.2 Mean Exposure at the MB by Gender

Table 4.3: Summary exposure statistics Gender at MB scenario.

Gender	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
FEMALE	0	0.613	0.037	0.034	0.017	0.029	0.044	0.091	0%
MALE	0	0.529	0.039	0.039	0.018	0.030	0.046	0.105	0%

Table 4.3 and Figure 4.3 shows that there is no significant difference between the two genders meaning same food consumption habits for male and female subjects.

Figure 4.3: Mean Exposure by Gender at MB scenario.

4.3 Mean Exposure at the MB by Area

Table 4.4: Summary exposure statistics by Area at MB scenario.

Area	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Ammochostos	0	0.486	0.039	0.041	0.016	0.029	0.045	0.102	0%
Larnaka	0	0.513	0.036	0.040	0.014	0.027	0.043	0.098	0%
Lefkosia	0	0.613	0.039	0.038	0.018	0.029	0.047	0.108	0%
Lemesos	0	0.529	0.039	0.034	0.021	0.032	0.046	0.089	0%
Pafos	0	0.324	0.034	0.027	0.019	0.030	0.044	0.071	0%

Figure 4.4: Mean Exposure by Area at MB scenario.

4.4 Mean Exposure at the MB by Population Class

Table 4.5: Summary exposure statistics by Population Class at MB scenario.

Population class	Min	Max	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	P95	pctOver
Adolescents	0.000	0.146	0.040	0.026	0.023	0.033	0.052	0.095	0%
Adults	0.002	0.086	0.029	0.016	0.016	0.026	0.040	0.059	0%
Elderly	0.002	0.125	0.032	0.022	0.017	0.026	0.041	0.076	0%
Infants	0.000	0.613	0.151	0.128	0.060	0.120	0.226	0.431	0%
Other children	0.004	0.513	0.074	0.050	0.043	0.062	0.097	0.157	0%
Toddlers	0.032	0.352	0.136	0.065	0.089	0.127	0.163	0.264	0%

In Table 4.5 and Figure 4.5 the exposure of each population class is shown. It was found that infants and toddlers had 2 or 3 times higher exposure than the other population classes. The lower body weight of these population classes is the main reason for the higher exposure. Also in all population classes the exposure was much lower than the ADI for Acetamiprid intake, 150 times lower for infants and toddlers and almost 1500 times lower for adults and elderly.

Figure 4.5: Mean Exposure by Population Class at MB scenario.

4.5 Mean Exposure at the MB scenario by [Area and Population class]

Figure 4.6 illustrates the mean exposure to Acetamiprid by population class and geographical area. It was found that there is no significant difference between the geographical areas in all population classes. The exposure seems to be independent of the geographical area. This is because the population in Cyprus has the same food consumption habits and the food categories that are contaminated by Acetamiprid are consumed by all population classes.

Figure 4.6: Cross Plot

4.6 Contributions of different food groups to the dietary exposure

The contribution of each main food group to the total Acetamiprid exposure is shown in Figure 4.7. In general fruits were the main contributors to the total Acetamiprid exposure. Apples (15.6%), Potatoes (12.9%), Olive oil (6.5%), Bananas (5.8%), Orange juice (5.5%), followed by grapes, oranges, cereal-based food and pears (2.4-2.8%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Acetamiprid intake. From the above main contributors only apples, grapes, pears and oranges were contaminated with Acetamiprid. The other food categories that appeared in the main contributors is the result of the overestimation of the exposure by the application of the substitution method in the occurrence data and their high consumption by the whole population.

Figure 4.7 shows the contribution of food items at FoodEx Level 4

Figure 4.7: Contribution to the Acetamiprid Total Exposure MB.

Table 4.6: Contribution to the Acetamiprid Total Exposure (MB). Food items at FoodEx2 Level 4 with greater than 1% contribution

Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4	Contribution
Grains and grain-based products	Cereals and cereal primary derivatives	Cereal grains (and cereal-like grains)	Rice and similar-	1.98%
Grains and grain-based products	Cereals and cereal primary derivatives	Cereal and cereal-like flours	Wheat flour	1.89%
Grains and grain-based products	Breakfast cereals	Processed and mixed breakfast cereals	Cereal flakes and similar	1.94%
Starchy roots or tubers and products thereof, sugar plants	Starchy roots and tubers	Potatoes and similar-	Potatoes	12.92%
Legumes, nuts, oilseeds and spices	Legumes	Pulses (dried legume seeds)	Beans (dry) and similar-	1.67%
Legumes, nuts, oilseeds and spices	Nuts, oilseeds and oilfruits	Tree nuts	Almonds and similar-	1.05%
Legumes, nuts, oilseeds and spices	Nuts, oilseeds and oilfruits	Oilseeds	Peanuts and similar-	1.07%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Citrus fruits	Oranges and similar-	2.51%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Pome fruits	Apples and similar-	15.64%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Pome fruits	Pears and similar-	2.42%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Berries and small fruits	Grapes and similar fruits	2.80%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Stone fruits	Peaches and similar-	1.67%
Fruit and fruit products	Fruit used as fruit	Miscellaneous fruits with inedible peel, large	Bananas and similar-	5.84%
Animal and vegetable fats and oils and primary derivatives thereof	Animal and vegetable fats/oils	Vegetable fats and oils, edible	Olive oils	6.53%

Level1	Level2	Level3	Level4	Contribution
Animal and vegetable fats and oils and primary derivatives thereof	Animal and vegetable fats/oils	Vegetable fats and oils, edible	Seed oils	1.79%
Fruit and vegetable juices and nectars (including concentrates)	Fruit / vegetable juices and nectars	Vegetable juices	Juice, tomato	1.86%
Fruit and vegetable juices and nectars (including concentrates)	Fruit / vegetable juices and nectars	Fruit juices (100% from named source)	Juice, apple	1.07%
Fruit and vegetable juices and nectars (including concentrates)	Fruit / vegetable juices and nectars	Fruit juices (100% from named source)	Juice, orange	5.51%
Fruit and vegetable juices and nectars (including concentrates)	Fruit / vegetable juices and nectars	Fruit juices (100% from named source)	Mixed fruit juice	1.22%
Food products for young population	Infant and follow-on formulae	Follow-on formulae	Follow-on formulae, liquid	1.49%
Food products for young population	Infant and follow-on formulae	Infant formulae	Infant formulae, liquid	1.70%
Food products for young population	Processed cereal-based food for infants and young children	Cereals with an added high protein food reconstituted	Cereals with an added high protein food reconstituted	2.44%

5 Uncertainties

The evaluation of the uncertainties in the exposure assessment of Acetamiprid has been performed following the guidance of the Opinion of the Scientific Committee related to Uncertainties in Dietary Exposure Assessment. Table 5.1 presents a summary of uncertainties, highlighting the main sources of uncertainty and providing an estimate whether each source of uncertainty is likely to lead to an over- or under-estimation of the calculated dietary exposure.

Table 5.1: Summary of qualitative evaluation of the impact of uncertainties on the dietary exposure to Acetamiprid.

Sources of uncertainty	Direction ¹
Different time frame between concentration data and consumption data	+/-
Long-term (chronic) exposure assessed from few days of consumption	+
Measurement error in amounts of food consumed	+/-
Measurement error in individual body weights	+/-
Assumptions taken into account for the preparation of occurrence data	+/-
Application of the substitution method on the preparation of occurrence data with high percentage of left-censored data	+
Level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy for the calculation of the exposure	+

¹ + = uncertainty with potential to cause over-estimation of exposure; - = uncertainty with potential to cause under-estimation of exposure

A number of uncertainties can be identified regarding the selection of parameters, such as Acetamiprid concentration levels in foodstuffs and consumption data.

The uncertainty related to the representativeness of the occurrence data for certain food commodities with respect to the number of samples is taken into account. Given the fact that the analytical results were generated with an LC-MS/MS method in an accredited laboratory, this adds only slightly to the uncertainty of the analytical results.

Some potentially important extrapolation uncertainties arise since an individual survey of food consumption is used to estimate dietary exposure over a timescale longer than the survey duration. Remaining uncertainties relate to the measurement error in amounts of consumed foodstuffs and individual body weights.

In ImproRisk occurrence and consumption data matching for the calculation of the exposure is performed based on a level up approach matching in the FoodEx2 exposure hierarchy, which may lead to overestimation of the exposure.

Furthermore, several assumption taken into account in the preparation of the occurrence data (data from EFSA, dilution factors, aggregation) may lead to some uncertainties.

6 Conclusions

Mean and 95th percentile exposure for the Middle-bound scenario were calculated as 0.038 and 0.097 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ b.w. per day. It was found that in all three scenarios (LB, MB, UB) the whole population was exposed much lower than the ADI value of 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{Kg}$ b.w. per day. Toddlers and infants had higher exposure than the other population classes due to their lower body weight. In all population classes the exposure was much lower than the ADI for Acetamiprid intake, 150 times lower for infants and toddlers and almost 1500 times lower for adults and elderly.

There was no significant difference in Acetamiprid intake between genders and geographical areas.

The contribution to the total Acetamiprid exposure was mainly from fruits. Apples (15.6%), Potatoes (12.9%), Olive oil (6.5), Bananas (5.8%), Orange juice (5.5%), followed by grapes, oranges, cereal-based food and pears (2.4-2.8%) were the food categories with the highest contribution to the Acetamiprid intake. Due to an overestimation of the exposure by the application of the substitution method in the occurrence data some food categories appeared in the main contributors even they were not contaminated with Acetamiprid. The most contaminated fruits were apples, grapes, pears and oranges.

7 References

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8 Abbreviations

Table 8.1: Abbreviations

Key	Description
BMDL	Benchmark dose lower limit (lower bound of benchmark dose interval)
b.w.	Body weight
LB	Lower bound
LOD	Limit of detection
MB	Middle bound
MoE	Margin of exposure
SD	Standard deviation
P25	25th percentile
P75	75th percentile
P95	95th percentile
UB	Upper bound
wcoeff	Weight coefficient

9 Appendices